

Determinant of Organization Effectiveness: Study in Government Organization of Pidie Jaya

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Abstract: This study aims to test the effect of employee engagement and organization trust on organization citizenship behaviour and its impact on organization Effectiveness. The object of this research is the government organization of Pidie Jaya with Echelon IV Officers as a respondent. The number of sample is determined by using proportional sampling technique and Slovin equation, and it provides 171 respondents. Data is analyzed using the path analysis with the SPSS program assistance. The findings describes that employee engagement, organization trust, organization citizenship behaviour and organization Effectiveness have been going well. For the verification test of direct effect provides: employee engagement effects organization citizenship behaviour; organization trust effects organization citizenship behaviour significantly; employee engagement effects organization Effectiveness significantly; organization trust effects organization effectiveness significantly, and; organization citizenship behaviour effects organization Effectiveness significantly. These all findings prove that the previous theories are still applicable, and these also apply in Government organization of Pidie Jaya District. The originality of this research is in its novelty in term of the object, time, and statistic approach. This result contributes to academic and research area in order to develop the next model and method. For the practical, this has verified that the variables in this research need more attention from the managers especially in organization related.

Keywords: Employee engagement, organization trust, organization citizenship behaviour and organization Effectiveness

I. Introduction

The level of success of an organization in achieving the goals set in an organization is a measure of the degree of organization Effectiveness. (Koyuncu, Burke and Fiksenbaum, 2006) in (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013) states that achieving organization Effectiveness is the main focus and goal of any organization, which for that requires great effort by maximizing task efficiency, commitment and maintaining employee motivation to work well.

The fact, to make the effectiveness in much organization is not easy. Government as a bureaucratic organization with lots of inflexibility makes them difficult to achieve the effectiveness performance. In Government of Pidie Jaya as an organization, there is still a tendency for employees to carry out in disciplinary actions, one of which is related to the submission of reports or data. There are numbers of employees who cannot complete the tasks given based on the time limit, and they are not be able to achieve the high quality of work determined by their superiors. This happens because the level of ability of employees in carrying out their duties and functions has not been evenly distributed in each work unit (SKPD). Most are in Echelon IV level as a first level of technical managers. The organization's ability to achieve its objectives is an indicator to see the success of an organization. Employee behavior greatly influences effectiveness in the organization, because employees are the main resource for all organizations. Effectiveness in organizations is an accumulation of effectiveness that exists in individual employees and groups. Individual effectiveness focuses on carrying out the duties and responsibilities of individuals as workers in an organization, while group effectiveness emphasizes on the performance produced by the work group as a team work. Effectiveness is a basis in seeing or measuring the level of success achieved by the organization for its intended purpose. An organization is said to be effective if the organization tends to produce more and more, and adaptable in solving problems (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013). (Daft, 1995) in (Zheng, Yang and McLean, 2010) defines organization Effectiveness as the level that an organization has in realizing its goals. (Mott, 1972) in (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013), defines organization

effectiveness as the ability of organizations to mobilize all abilities for action, production and adaptation. According to (Lewin and Minton, 1986) in (Eydi, 2015), organization Effectiveness measurements are carried out through competing value approaches, that are : 1) Open System, which is the flexibility and ability to get resources; 2) Rational Goals, namely the existence of certain plans or objectives and high productivity and efficiency; 3) Internal Process, which emphasizes on humans and control and information dissemination and stability and tranquility in assessing organization effectiveness, and; 4) Human Relations, namely the existence of an integrated / cohesive and skilled workforce.

In an effort to achieve an optimal of organization Effectiveness, this cannot be separated from the influence of employee engagement. This is consistent with the facts stated by (Welch, 2011) in (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013) that among optimism, trust and attachment, leaders and managers throughout the world recognize employee engagement as an important component that can influence the level of organization Effectiveness. This is why the latest efforts to improve organization performance have begun to embed positive organization concepts such as optimism, trust and attachment. Many researches conclude that bound employees are more committed to helping organizations in achieving goals. Besides that they also have a greater possibility to provide input or ideas for the good of the organization in the future. (Saks, 2008) states that bound employees are more likely to do things in an effort to improve organization Effectiveness, because they have a large sense of attachment (Engaged) with their work and organization (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004).

In the Government of Pidie Jaya, based on observation of authors shows that there is still low employee engagement happened. The phenomenon occurred is the low commitment of employees to help the organization in achieving its goals, including the tendency of some employees to show an inaction attitude toward the difficulties experienced by the organization, being passive in providing input or ideas for their organization. Employee engagement has a positive relationship with organization Effectiveness, therefore employee engagement is currently the main focus of various organizations (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013). (Kahn, 1990) defines employee engagement as a form of effort to bind themselves to members of the organization with their role in the organization. (Saks, 2006) cites several opinions stating that employee engagement is a form of commitment to the organization. (Shuck and Wollard, 2010) in (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013) defines employee engagement as the cognitive, emotional and behavioral conditions of each individual employee who focuses on the desired results. (Albrecht, 2010), defines employee engagement as a commitment from individual employees to their organizations that are able to move employees to show the best in improving performance. In addition to employee engagement, organization trust is another factor that can influence the organization efforts to achieve organization Effectiveness (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013).

Other than that, trust is a very important aspect to be applied in an organization. With the establishment of trust there will be an advantage in the internal organization which of course will have a huge impact on the organization. This is supported by the statement from (Altuntas and Baykal, 2010), that trust is something important in establishing relationships in an organization, especially the relationship between employees and leaders. In (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013) explains that the dimensions of employee engagement measurements are: 1) Vigor, which is a behavior characterized by high outpouring of positive energy and strong mentality in completing a job and diligent in resolving the difficulties encountered during work; 2) Dedication, which is the feeling of strong emotional involvement between employees and their jobs; 3) Absorption, which is a behavior in which employees enjoy and are happy in working with full concentration and seriousness.

In the Government organization of Pidie Jaya district, trust is in the low level of satisfaction or happiness. Toward the organization, the employees feeling treated unfairly and honestly, and the attitude of organizations that are less concerned about their employees. The level of employee confidence maintaining its commitment also affects the trust of employees towards their organization. Trust is an important element in establishing a relationship, in business management and organization communication the emphasis is on relationships between managers and between managers and subordinates (Paine, 2003). (Rousseau *et al.*, 2012) in (Robbins and Judge, 2012) states that trust is a psychological state of an individual who has a positive expectation of something. (Schoorman, Mayer and Davis, 2007) in (Lin, 2010), states that organization trust is trust in an organization that involves the willingness of employees to be vulnerable to actions or their organization's policies. This willingness can only be given when an organization communicates clearly what actions or organization policies have on employees formally and informally (Tan and LIM, 2009). According to (Bromiley and Cummings, 1992) in (Altuntas and Baykal, 2010) states that organization trust is trust that arises from individuals and groups as a whole, that individuals or organizations will mobilize all abilities with good intentions and commitments without hidden ill intentions. (Katou, 2013) explains that organization trust can be measured through three dimensions, namely: 1) Integrity, which is a form of belief that the organization will be fair and honest; 2) Competence, which is an attitude that shows confidence in the ability of the organization; 3) Dependability, which is an attitude that shows confidence in the organization's commitment to itself.

This certainly can trigger employees desire to move from one agency to another even though there is no increase in position / echelon due to loss of trust in the organization; decreases work motivation and loss of employee willingness to display organization citizenship behaviour. In the study of (Donghwan Yoon, Jichul Jang, 2016) states that organization trust affects the willingness of employees to display organization citizenship behaviour. This is because when employees consider their organization to be trustworthy, they will willingly display work behavior beyond their employment contract. Chiang and (Hsieh, 2012) in (Donghwan Yoon, Jichul Jang, 2016) describes that organization trust is the driving force for the emergence of significant organization citizenship behaviour because it is able to motivate employees' own behavior starting from themselves. And this will ultimately give a bad influence to the organization in an effort to achieve organization Effectiveness. In (Kataria, Garg and Rastogi, 2013) notes that organization citizenship behaviour has an influence and make a very meaningful contribution to the organization, because it can increase the effectiveness, efficiency and overall performance of the organization by lubricating the social machinery of the organization, reducing friction and increasing efficiency. The fact occurred in government organization of Pidie Jaya district is the reluctance of employees to take the initiative themselves to help or take over the work of their co-workers who are having difficulties in completing their tasks or excessively voluntarily without being asked by their supervisor to help. There is a lack of employee awareness of the development of the organization and in providing encouragement or motivation to other coworkers. According to (Popescu, Deaconu and Popescu, 2015), the dimensions of measurement of organization citizenship behaviour are : 1). Altruism, which is initiative behavior from employees in helping coworkers in one organization; 2) Courtesy, namely the behavior of avoiding problems due to work by giving advice and input and appreciating what they need; 3) Sportsmanship, namely behavior that shows tolerance to the organization; 4) Civic Virtue, is an attitude that shows concern for the survival of the organization and wants to participate or be involved in organization activities, and ; 5) Conscientiousness, which is to do things that have a positive and beneficial impact on the organization. organization citizenship behaviour is the choice of behavior of individual employees without any element of coercion that can benefit the organization in increasing productivity (Sharma, Bajpai and Holani, 2010) In (Nyoman, Suwandewi and Sintaasih, 2016). organization citizenship behaviour can also be interpreted as a mutually helpful attitude between fellow members of the organization that is positive and builds both for employees and their organizations (Steers, Porter and Bigley, 1996) in (Purba and Seniati, 2004). According to Purba and Nina (2004), organization citizenship behaviour is behavior that is the initiative and choice of individuals because it has no relationship with the organization's formal reward system but is able to boost effectiveness in an organization. Organization citizenship behaviour is not a formal obligation of employees, so that if they are not shown they will not get sanctions.

Based on the above theories and problems, then it can be conclude the research paradigm as follows.

Figure1. Research Paradigm

From the figure 1, it concludes that the hypothesis research which is formulated:

- H1 : employee engagement effects organization citizenship behaviour;
- H2 : organization trust effects organization citizenship behaviour significantly;
- H3 : employee engagement effects organization Effectiveness significantly;
- H4 : organization trust effects organization Effectiveness significantly
- H5 : organization citizenship behaviour effects organization Effectiveness significantly

II. Method

This research type is a verification research. This verifies the causality of the variables based on the theories. Pidie Jaya Regency is as the place to conduct the study, which is in its all SKPD (unit of executors) within. The population is employees in level of echelon IV, that is as a first level of technical managers, as much as 297 people. Then the sampling technique used is proportional sampling, and Slovin equation is used to calculate the number of samples with an error or error of 5% (Nadeak, 2018), which is as follows.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

- n: Number of samples used
- N: Total population, which is 297 people
- e: 5% error limit

And by Slovin equation it provides 171 respondents as the sample. The data is analyzed using path analysis with SPSS as a statistics application. And the path equation can be figured as follows.

Sub Structure 1 : $Y = PYX_1 + PYX_2 + \epsilon_1$

Sub Structure 2 : $Z = PZX_1 + PZX_2 + PZY + \epsilon_2$

- Z = organization effectiveness
- X1 = employee engagement
- X2 = organization trust
- Y = organization citizenship behaviour
- P = path coefficient
- ϵ_1 = Structural error
- ϵ_2 = Structural error

III. Result

Figure2. Path Analysis Test Result

The hypothesis test result explains as follows:

Table1. The Effect of Employee Engagement And Organization Trust on Organization Citizenship Behaviour

Nama Variabel	Unstandardize d Coef.	Standardized Coef.	T _{count}	Sig
	B	Beta		
Constant	2.891			
Employee engagement (X ₁)	0.164	0.525	5.001	0.000
Organization trust (X ₂)	0.117	0.315	2.996	0.004
R	= 0.706		F _{count}	= 26.328
R _{square}	= 0.498		F _{Table}	= 3.049
			Sig.	= 0.000

Hypothesis 1 (accepted)

Employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on organization citizenship behaviour, with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and the Beta Coefficient value of 0.525. This illustrates that if the employee engagement increases 1 unit, it will increase organization citizenship behaviour 0.525 units

Hypothesis 2 (accepted)

Organization trust has a positive and significant effect on organization citizenship behaviour, with the significant value of $0.004 < 0.05$ and the Beta Coefficient value of 0.315. This indicates that if the organization trust increases 1 unit, it will increase organization citizenship behaviour 0.315 unit

Based on Table 1 it is known that simultaneously the variables of organization trust and employee engagement have a significant effect on organization citizenship behaviour, this is indicated by the value of $F_{Count} > F_{Table}$ ($26.328 > 3.049$) at the significance level of 0,000.

Table2. The Effect of Employee Engagement and Organization Trust on Organization Effectiveness

Nama Variabel	Unstandardiz ed Coef.	Standardiz ed Coef.	T _{count}	Sig
	B	Beta		
Constant	2.651			
Employee engagement (X ₁)	0.164	0.335	2.660	0.010
Organization trust (X ₂)	0.175	0.301	2.395	0.020
R	= 0.528		F _{count}	= 10.241
R _{square}	= 0.279		F _{table}	= 3.049
			Sig.	= 0.000

Hypothesis 3 (accepted)

Employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on organization Effectiveness, with the significant value of $0.010 < 0.05$ and the Beta Coefficient value of 0.335. This figures that if the employee engagement increases 1 unit, it will increase organization effectiveness 0.335 units.

Hypothesis 4 (accepted)

Organization trust has a positive and significant effect on organization Effectiveness, with the significant value of $0.020 < 0.05$ and a Beta Coefficient of 0.301. This means that if the employee organization trust increases 1 unit, it will increase organization effectiveness 0.301 unit.

Based on Table 2 it is known that simultaneously the variables of organization trust and employee engagement

have a significant effect on organization Effectiveness, this is indicated by the value of $F_{\text{Count}} > F_{\text{Table}}$ ($10.241 > 3.049$) at the significance level of 0.000.

Table3. The Effect of Organization Citizenship Behaviour on Organization Effectiveness

Nama Variabel	Unstandar dized Coef.	Standardized Coef.	T _{count}	Sig
	B	Beta		
Constant	2.064			
Organization Citizenship Behaviour (Y)	0.471	0.735	7.964	0.000
R	= 0.735		F _{count}	= 63.424
R _{square}	= 0.540		F _{Table}	= 3.049
			Sig.	= 0.000

Hypothesis 5 (accepted)

Organization citizenship behaviour has a positive and significant effect on organization Effectiveness, with a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and Beta Keofisien value of 0.735. This describes that if the organization citizenship behaviour increases 1 unit, it will increase organization effectiveness 0.735 unit

From Table 3 it is known that simultaneously the organization citizenship behaviour variable has a significant effect on organization Effectiveness, with the value of $F_{\text{Count}} > F_{\text{Table}}$ ($63.424 > 3.049$) at the Significance level of 0.000.

From all findings we can see all tests are verified in line with the previous theories, that the causality tests in the variables of this research have causality relationships. This has an implication to academic and science that this is an update of theories and to enrich the realm of science. And also for the real practice, the government of Pidie Jaya can use this to findings as a reference to increase the organization engagement, organization trust, and organization citizenship behaviour in the level of echelon IV to enhance its organization effectiveness. This can be operate by formulating the right policies and implementing it in the organization. This also can be a uniqe reference as this object is a government organization which has a bureaucratic type of organization.

IV. Conclusion

The result shows that descriptively the employee engagement, organization trust, organization citizenship behaviour and organization Effectiveness have been going well. For the verification test of direct effect provides: employee engagement effects organization citizenship behaviour; organization trust effects organization citizenship behaviour significantly; employee engagement effects organization Effectiveness significantly; organization trust effects organization Effectiveness significantly, and; organization citizenship behaviour effects organization Effectiveness significantly.. These all findings prove that the previous theories are still applicable, and these also apply in Government organization of Pidie Jaya District. The originality of this research is in its novelty in term of the object, time, and statistic approach. This result contributes to academic and research area in order to develop the next model and method. This research model also can enrich the realm of knowledge and science. For the practical, this has verified that the variables in this research need more attention from the managers especially in organization related. All causality relationships among variables is very necessary to be maintained with managerial skills of the policy makers.

Reference

- [1.] Albrecht, S. L. (2010) *Research and Practice. Handbook of Employee Engagement Perspective, Issues*. UK: MGP Books Group. Cheltenham, UK • Northampton, MA, USA.
- [2.] Altuntas, S. and Baykal, U. (2010) 'Relationship between nurses' organizational trust levels and their organizational citizenship behaviors', *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 42(2), pp. 186-194. doi: 10.1111/j.1547-5069.2010.01347.x.
- [3.] Bromiley, P. and Cummings, L. L. (1992) *Transactions costs in organizations with trust*. Stamford, CT: JAI Press Inc.

- [4.] Daft, R. L. (1995) 'No More Tears', *Journal of Management Education*. Tenth Edit. USA: South-Western Cengage Learning, 19(1), pp. 31–34. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/105256299501900105>.
- [5.] Donghwan Yoon, Jichul Jang, J. (Jay) L. (2016) 'Environmental management strategy and organizational citizenship behaviors in the hotel industry', *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(8), pp. 1–43. doi: 10.1108/IJCHM-10-2014-0498.
- [6.] Eydi, H. (2015) 'Analysis of Organizational Effectiveness Approaches (Case Study: Sporting Organizations Field)', *Intenational Journal Of managemen Science*, X(January 2015).
- [7.] Hsieh, S. Y. (2012) 'An exploratory study of complaints handling and nature', *International Journal of Nursing Practice*, 18(5), pp. 471–480. doi: 10.1111/j.1440-172X.2012.02057.x.
- [8.] Kahn, W. A. (1990) 'Psychological conditions of personal engagement and disengagement at work', *Academy of management journal*. Academy of Management Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510, 33(4), pp. 692–724.
- [9.] Kataria, A., Garg, P. and Rastogi, R. (2013) 'Employee Engagement and Organizational Effectiveness: The Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior', 6(1).
- [10.] Katou, A. A. (2013) 'The link between HR practices, psychological contract fulfilment, and organisational performance in Greece: An economic crisis perspective', *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 6(2), pp. 568–594. doi: 10.3926/jiem.501.
- [11.] Koyuncu, M., Burke, R. J. and Fiksenbaum, L. (2006) 'Work engagement among women managers and professionals in a Turkish bank', *Equal Opportunities International*, 25(4), pp. 299–310. doi: 10.1108/02610150610706276.
- [12.] Lewin, A. Y. and Minton, J. W. (1986) 'Determining organizational effectiveness: Another look, and an agenda for research', *Management science*. INFORMS, 32(5), pp. 514–538. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.32.5.514>.
- [13.] Lin, C. P. (2010) 'Modeling corporate citizenship, organizational trust, and work engagement based on attachment theory', *Journal of Business Ethics*, 94(4), pp. 517–531. doi: 10.1007/s10551-009-0279-6.
- [14.] Mott, P. E. (1972) *The characteristics of effective organizations*. New York: HarperCollins Publishers.
- [15.] Nyoman, N., Suwandewi, T. and Sintaasih, D. K. (2016) 'Keadilan Organisasional Dan Komitmen Organisasional: Efeknya Pada Organizational Citizenship Behavior Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Udayana , Bali , Indonesia Keberhasilan suatu perusahaan bukan hanya didukung oleh aspek keuangan yang berupa pe', *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*, 5(7), pp. 4453–4485.
- [16.] Paine, K. D. (2003) 'Guidelines for measuring trust in organizations', *The institute for public relations*, 2003, pp. 9–10.
- [17.] Popescu, A. M., Deaconu, A. and Popescu, T. (2015) 'Organization's Age and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Performance Criteria at SMEs Level. Case Study - Bucharest - Ilfov Development Region', *Procedia Economics and Finance*. Elsevier B.V., 22(November 2014), pp. 645–654. doi: 10.1016/s2212-5671(15)00278-6.
- [18.] Purba, E. D. and Seniati, A. N. L. (2004) 'Pengaruh kepribadian dan komitmen organisasi terhadap', *Makara, Sosial Humaniora*, 8(3), pp. 105–111.
- [19.] Robbins, S. P. and Judge, T. A. (2012) *Organizational Behavior*. 15th edn. Edited by S. Yagan. San Diego: Pearson.
- [20.] Rousseau, D. M. et al. (2012) 'To Special Topic Forum Not So Different After All : a Cross- Discipline View of Trust', *Academy of Management Review*, 23(3), pp. 393–404.
- [21.] Saks, A. M. (2006) 'Employee engagement: Antecedents and consequences', *Journal of managerial psychology*, 21(7), pp. 600–619.
- [22.] Saks, A. M. (2008) 'The Meaning and Bleeding of Employee Engagement: How Muddy Is the Water?', *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 1(1), pp. 40–43. doi: 10.1111/j.1754-9434.2007.00005.x.
- [23.] Schaufeli, W. and Bakker, A. (2004) *Utrecht Work Enggament Scale (UWES)*. Netherlands: Occupational Health

Psychology Unit Utrecht University.

- [24.] Schoorman, F. D., Mayer, R. C. and Davis, J. H. (2007) 'An integrative model of organizational trust: Past, present, and future', *Academy of Management Review*. Academy of Management Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510, 32(2), pp. 344-354.
- [25.] Sharma, J. P., Bajpai, N. and Holani, U. (2010) 'Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Public and Private Sector and Its Impact on Job Satisfaction: A Comparative Study in Indian Perspective', *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(1), pp. 67-75. doi: 10.5539/ijbm.v6n1p67.
- [26.] Shuck, B. and Wollard, K. (2010) 'Employee engagement and HRD: A seminal review of the foundations', *Human Resource Development Review*, 9(1), pp. 89-110. doi: 10.1177/1534484309353560.
- [27.] Steers, R. M., Porter, L. W. and Bigley, G. A. (1996) *Motivation and Leadership at Work*. 6th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [28.] Tan, H. H. and LIM, A. K. H. (2009) 'Trust in Coworkers and Trust in Organizations', *The Journal of Psychology*, 143(1), pp. 45-66.
- [29.] Welch, M. (2011) 'The evolution of the employee engagement concept: Communication implications', *Corporate Communications*, 16(4), pp. 328-346. doi: 10.1108/13563281111186968.
- [30.] Zheng, W., Yang, B. and McLean, G. N. (2010) 'Linking organizational culture, structure, strategy, and organizational effectiveness: Mediating role of knowledge management', *Journal of Business research*. Elsevier, 63(7), pp. 763-771.